

ONLINE ACCOUNTABILITY AND LOCAL GOVERNMENTS: THE CASE OF METROPOLITAN MUNICIPALITIES *¹

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Abstract

The transformation brought by Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) is reshaping organizational structures and the functioning of administrative systems in contemporary societies. With the transition of public institutions to digital platforms, these technological developments are redefining the principles of transparency, governance, and accountability that dominate traditional service delivery models. Within public institutions, new norms and practices such as open data have emerged under a more inclusive governance framework. The multilayered impact of digitalization technically enables metropolitan municipalities, in particular, to enhance stakeholder participation and guarantee the right to access information through structured data ecosystems via web-based platforms. The strengthening of metropolitan municipalities' digital capacities through open data policies, the institutionalization of data standards, and platform-based interaction mechanisms contributes to increased levels of transparency and accountability. This article aims to analyze the concept of "online accountability" and evaluate the extent to which metropolitan municipalities communicate their activities, decisions, and justifications to stakeholders via digital platforms, thereby ensuring transparency and accountability in governance. This study, conducted through a qualitative descriptive analysis of the online accountability of metropolitan municipalities in Turkey, uses tables and content analyses as its primary sources. Although these analyses are based on datasets collected during the thesis process in 2022, they have been updated as of 2025. This article aims to offer an evaluative perspective on accountability in the digitalization of local governments and, as the first study in this field, to establish a theoretical and methodological foundation for future academic research.

Keywords: Web Based Accountability, Local Governments, E-Government, Accountability, ICT.

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1.Introduction

The rapid advancements in information technologies have become a significant component in strengthening governance, particularly in terms of local governments utilizing digital platform mechanisms to deliver services (Lee & Joseph, 2012, p.170). Thanks to the high data processing capacity and comprehensive information management capabilities provided by technology, public services can be delivered more effectively and efficiently, thereby reinforcing the institutional accountability capacity of local governments (Trabelsia et al., 2008, p.132). Digital platforms not only enhance accountability mechanisms but also expand access to services and information provided by local governments, making public oversight in governance more functional (Ariesmansyah et al., 2021, p.14061). In this process, accountability functions as an inquiry mechanism that enables the evaluation of activities performed or not performed by institutions in the course of achieving their defined strategic objectives within corporate governance and operational processes (Çınar, 2015, p.13).

The delivery of public services through web-based platforms has expanded the scope of online accountability practices by enabling the direct and timely sharing of information, thereby necessitating adherence to the principle of transparency (Sary Kezia et al., 2021, p.65). In local governments, online accountability is shaped by the quantitative and qualitative dimensions of financial disclosures and performance reports; local governments that demonstrate their institutional characteristics through online transparency associate these two elements with accountability in terms of performance and financial reporting quality (Nair et al., 2022, s.17). The transparent sharing of information regarding local government activities reflects the qualitative dimension by enhancing the level of interaction with stakeholders and strengthening institutional trust in the administration (Patrucco et al., 2021, p.632).

Online accountability practices are not limited to the online analysis of websites; they are also directly concerned with the content of the disclosed data and how stakeholders access this information (Dumont, 2013, p.8). In direct relation to data content and access strategies, official websites and similar public data portals have been established by local governments to provide access to open data (Lourenço & Serra, 2014, p.38). The functionality of these platforms is closely linked to providing information, setting objectives, reporting outcomes, and evaluating activities in terms of accountability. Through interactive data sharing at the institutional level,

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they enable stakeholders to actively participate in monitoring and evaluation processes (Sintejudeanu & Farcas, 2017, p.33).

With the increasing capacity of digitalization to align with transparency and accountability policies, online accountability tools have gained institutional-level prevalence in local government practices worldwide (Shahib & Risky, 2017, p.60). This article, the first original study conducted in Türkiye in this field, aims to address the institutional gap in the literature. It examines the online accountability levels of metropolitan municipalities in Türkiye and analyzes their practices using a qualitative descriptive method. During the research process, data will be manually collected from the official websites of metropolitan municipalities through qualitative thematic coding. The study investigates the concepts of accountability and online accountability based on the literature on local governments. In the conclusion section, strategies focused on institutional governance are proposed based on the findings regarding the online accountability levels of metropolitan municipalities.

2. Accountability and Online Accountability: Theoretical Foundations and Conceptual Framework

Accountability is the concept whereby an individual explains the reasons for their actions or inactions and assumes responsibility for the consequences of those actions (Roberts, 2002, p.658). In the management literature, accountability requires that institutional actors at the normative level be traceable to external stakeholders regarding the outcomes of their decisions and actions (Mulgan, 2000, p.575). From a governance perspective, accountability refers to a multi-actor network of oversight and responsibility, transitioning from traditional hierarchical chains of command and control to a structure based on collaboration and negotiation, as required by governance paradigms (Aytar, 2022, p.9). In terms of digitalization, accountability necessitates a more comprehensive understanding of governance, including the ethical responsibility of technological systems that design and operate digital infrastructures. In this context, administrative processes become more transparent and traceable through e-government applications, open data platforms, and digital participation tools with data-driven governance formats (Tejedo-Romero et al., 2022, p.1).

Advancements in information and communication technologies have undertaken innovative functions such as digital infrastructure, data-driven traceability, and algorithmic transparency

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in addressing these deficiencies and closing the accountability gap in governance mechanisms (Biricikoğlu & Eryılmaz, 2011, p.31). This transformation is not abrupt; it requires institutional alignment and capacity. Moreover, it is crucial for institutions and stakeholders to gradually adapt to this process through digital transformation strategies (Garcia et al., 2015, p.1208). Strengthening transparency and communication through web-based applications promotes the operational functionality of accountability and the effective implementation of digital performance indicators. Accordingly, a governance model infrastructure has been established through online accountability, based on platform-driven transparency, data-sharing regimes, and digital responsibility (Carvalho et al., 2020, p.44). The concept of online accountability refers to digital tools that support reciprocal information flow by disclosing online information such as budget reports, public procurement decisions, and council resolutions on websites, helping organizations demonstrate and enhance their accountability (Cooley, 2020, p.1426). Saxton & Guo (2011) conceptualize online accountability in two dimensions: disclosure and dialogue. The first dimension, disclosure, consists of two sub-dimensions: financial disclosure and performance disclosure.

Financial disclosure involves the publication of compliance-related documents such as online budgeting materials, reports on the use of financial resources, administrative fees for funds, fund management, and performance information (Lee & Joseph, 2013, p.2218). It refers to an external accountability process supported by quantitative and qualitative indicators, enabling the tracking of an organization's voluntarily disclosed financial data and progress over time via its website (Saxton, 2014, p.132). The disclosure of an institution's financial statements and the evaluation of its financial status through web-based technologies make institutional effectiveness measurable, while the disclosure of performance data determines the institution's efficiency and effectiveness, enhances the credibility of information sharing, and improves stakeholder relations (Khoufi et al., 2018, p.701). Performance disclosure is defined as the presentation of goal- and outcome-oriented information published on an organization's website; organizational performance is typically expressed as the measurement of an event or process at the input, activity, output, or outcome level for a specific objective (Brusca & Montesinos, 2016, p.508). The financial information available on publicly accessible websites allows stakeholders to easily access performance data, evaluate the organization's performance, obtain performance-related information on decisions and solutions, and develop effective

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communication skills for achieving mission and vision objectives (Lourenço et al., 2013, p.282).

The second dimension of online accountability, dialogue, reveals how organizations explain their actions through reciprocal communication mechanisms involving stakeholder feedback and interactive participation processes (Dubnick, 2005, p.381). The first component of dialogue, stakeholder input, serves as an intermediary mechanism that facilitates information exchange between the organization and its stakeholders. Stakeholder input refers to the organization's consideration of opinions, suggestions, information, or feedback received from stakeholders in its decision-making processes (Lappas et al., 2021, p.90). Buss and colleagues (2006) emphasize that stakeholder feedback plays a significant role in enhancing the credibility and legitimacy of organizations. The second component, interactive participation, is defined as an effective mechanism for transferring information from the institution to stakeholders through processes designed for specific stakeholder groups (Kim & Lee, 2017, p.3). Interactive participation enables the collection of targeted feedback, demands, complaints, and preferences between the administration and stakeholders through the services provided. Furthermore, it supports new opportunities for collaborative knowledge production within a decentralized structure characterized by high participation (Sun & Sunder, 2022, p.2). In this context, the execution of institutional activities via digital platforms has increased stakeholder access to information through participation mechanisms responsive to stakeholder preferences, thereby making web-based accountability feasible at the local level (Robbins et al., 2008, p.569).

2.1. The Impact of Online Accountability Practices on Metropolitan Municipalities within Local Government Units

The delivery of public services through web-based platforms has expanded the scope of online accountability practices by enabling the direct and timely sharing of information (Kluvers, 2003, p.58). Web platforms have facilitated the integration of paper-based procedures into digital systems within local governments, allowing for faster operations, reduced errors, more efficient resource utilization, and more accurate processing (Kloot, 1999, p.566). Consequently, they have increased the availability of large volumes of information in digital environments, simplified the presentation of data through effective compilation, and emphasized the

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importance of encouraging stakeholders' active participation in online settings (Özata & Sevinç, 2010, p.73).

With the widespread use of information and communication technologies in service delivery by metropolitan municipalities, which are local government units, web-based accountability has become one of the tools for active participation, enabling the provision of fast and effective services to users through digital platforms such as email, online databases, and blogs (İlgin & Ulupınar, 2020, p.111). This has increased trust among stakeholders by presenting information in various content formats such as videos, data downloads, and presentations, allowing stakeholders to access public services rapidly (Gajewski & Li Li, 2015, p.116). Digital platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp also facilitate interactive participation and support the process of expressing community concerns. This plays a significant role in enabling effective communication with administrators and ensuring the efficient delivery of online accountability and services (Ahmad, 2020, p.303).

Digital technologies offer capabilities such as traceability of decision-making processes and administrative activities, providing stakeholders with the opportunity to evaluate the effectiveness and efficiency of metropolitan municipalities (Putri et al., 2021, p.463). In this context, they serve as a tool for accessing the annual activity reports of metropolitan municipalities based on performance disclosures (Ammons & Rivenbark, 2008, p.304). Accessing financial information through digital platforms and especially publishing financial and fiscal reports in digital environments plays a role in strengthening accountability and enhancing transparency (Bakar & Saleh, 2016, p.159). The information and services provided by metropolitan municipalities through web platforms vary according to the maturity level of their technological infrastructure. This situation has led to the development of digital governance approaches regarding stakeholders' access to information (Şat, 2016, p.188).

2.2. Online Accountability Practices of Metropolitan Municipalities: The Case of Türkiye

When examining studies on the two fundamental dimensions of online accountability—disclosure and dialogue—in Türkiye, no research specifically focused on metropolitan municipalities is found, indicating a gap in the literature. However, various legal regulations that have led to the implementation of web-based accountability practices have been

EMIDWORLD 3rd International Congress on Economics Public Finance Business & Social Sciences institutionalized. In this regard, Law No. 5018 mandates public administrations to publish budget information in order to ensure transparency in financial management and provide access to information within the scope of authority and responsibility in audit and expenditure processes (Yaman & Gökalp, 2017, p.9). Under Law No. 5302 on Provincial Special Administration, local governments are obliged to transparently disclose their financial resources to improve efficiency, quality, and effectiveness in public services through activity reporting and strategic planning related to their performance (Kara & Karakılıç, 2016, p.729). Another regulation concerning performance presentation, within the framework of relevant provisions of Law No. 6085 on the Court of Accounts and Law No. 5393 on Municipalities, aims to enhance the accountability of metropolitan municipalities by evaluating local government activities according to specific performance indicators and presenting these data to the public based on targets and indicators (Sezer & Büyükpınar, 2021, p.97). Between 2003 and 2007, the Ministry of Interior established the Municipal Performance Monitoring System, through which data were collected from municipalities and analyzed via the YEREL BİLGİ system (Eroğlu, 2019, p.548). To increase stakeholder participation, in line with the transparency principle of Law No. 5393, documents related to municipal decision-making processes (council and commission decisions) have been made publicly accessible. Furthermore, within the framework of digital transformation in public administration, the e-Government Gateway was established in 2008 pursuant to Law No. 4982, Law No. 5216, Law No. 5070 on Electronic Signatures, and the 2006 Prime Ministry Circular, aiming to expand digital access to public services (Gençkaya & Gündoğdu, 2021, p.708). These regulations have been supported by reforms aimed at increasing stakeholder participation, creating a platform for online accountability, and promoting the sharing of policy information through quality feedback (Kim & Lee, 2017, p.2).

3. Methodology

This section presents the research design, data collection and analysis methods, and the scope of the study in detail. The transparency and replicability of the research process are prioritized.

3.1. Purpose and Scope of the Study

The population of this study consists of metropolitan municipalities in Türkiye. The research aims to evaluate the impact of online accountability on metropolitan municipalities. Within this

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population, the official websites of metropolitan municipalities are examined over a limited period, and the effectiveness of their practices in terms of online accountability is analyzed.

3.2. Research Method

This study was conducted to assess the level of online accountability in metropolitan municipalities in Türkiye. Using a qualitative descriptive research method, the official websites of 30 metropolitan municipalities in Türkiye were examined in detail between 06.09.2022 and 30.11.2022, and data obtained from updates made between 07.01.2025 and 20.02.2025 were also included in the analysis.

3.3. Data Collection and Analysis Process

The analysis of web-based accountability focuses on two main dimensions: disclosure and dialogue. The disclosure dimension is evaluated under two subcategories: financial disclosures and performance disclosures; the dialogue dimension is assessed through stakeholder input and interactive participation. These dimensions were evaluated based on 22 criteria identified through a literature review.

The data analysis, based on Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis process, initially focuses on whether detailed disclosure criteria are present on the websites of metropolitan municipalities, their accessibility, and the informational effectiveness of this access. The study analyzes public information access on the websites of 30 metropolitan municipalities and evaluates the prevalence of web-based accountability distribution practices.

3.4. Literature Review

To examine the websites of metropolitan municipalities, criteria were established based on scientific studies on the concept of online accountability in national and international literature. A web scan was conducted using key concepts such as "online accountability," "financial disclosure," "performance disclosure," "interactive participation," and "online accountability in local governments," and a corresponding evaluation table was prepared based on the findings. As of 2025, there are 30 metropolitan municipalities in Türkiye, and their levels of web-based accountability have been assessed under four subcategories: performance disclosure, financial disclosure, stakeholder input, and interactive participation. These criteria were systematically determined using sources from the academic literature and are presented below.

Performance Disclosure (Dissemination): The criteria used in the study are based on the following academic sources: Capa Perez, C. M., Rodriguez Boliver, M. P., & Lopez Hernandez, M. A. (2014), “The Determinants of Government Financial Reports Online”; Carvalho, A., Ferrira, R. M., & Lima (2020), “Web Disclosure of Institutional Information in Nonprofit Organizations: An Approach in Portuguese Charities”; Gençkaya, Ö. F., Gündoğdu, H. G., & Aytekin, A. (2021), “Evaluation of Metropolitan Municipalities’ Websites in Terms of Governance Principles.”

Financial Disclosure (Dissemination): The criteria used in the study are based on the following academic sources: Gençkaya, Ö. F., Gündoğdu, H. G., & Aytekin, A. (2021), “Evaluation of Metropolitan Municipalities’ Websites in Terms of Governance Principles”; Carvalho, A., Ferrira, R. M., & Lima (2020), “Web Disclosure of Institutional Information in Nonprofit Organizations: An Approach in Portuguese Charities”; Caba Perez, C. M., Rodriguez Bolivar, M. P., & Lopez Hernandez, M. A. (2014), “The Determinants of Government Financial Reports Online”; García Tabuyo, M., Sáez-Martín, A., & Caba-Pérez, M. D. (2016), “Mandatory versus Voluntary Disclosures: Drivers of Proactive Information Provision by Local Governments in Central America.” Based on these sources, 5 criteria were identified.

Stakeholder Input: The criteria used in the study are based on the following academic source: Carvalho, A., Ferrira, R. M., & Lima (2020), “Web Disclosure of Institutional Information in Nonprofit Organizations: An Approach in Portuguese Charities.” A total of 8 criteria were obtained.

Interactive Participation: The criteria used in the study are based on the following academic source: Midin, M., Joseph, C., & Mohamed, N. (2017), “Promoting Societal Governance: Stakeholders’ Engagement Disclosure on Malaysian Local Authorities’ Websites.” A total of 5 criteria were obtained. The 22 distinct criteria were classified under the two main dimensions of web-based accountability “disclosure” and “dialogue”—and are presented in the table below.

Table 3.1. Dimensions of Online Accountability and Evaluation Criteria

**Disclosure Sub-
Dimensions**

a: Are there any details regarding annual activity reports? (Carvalho et al., 2020, p.49)

b: Are budget reports, preliminary reports, and year-end reports published?

Performance

Disclosure

c: Are the short- and long-term activity reports available on the website? (Is there a reference to the strategic plan?) (Caba Perez et al., 2014, pp.7–8)

d: Does the metropolitan municipality's website provide information on council days/decisions/minutes? (Gençkaya & Gündoğdu, 2021, p.713)

a: Is the budget available on the website? (Garcia & Garcia, 2010, p.683)

b: Are public procurement and purchasing transactions announced?

Financial

Disclosure

c: Are there financial reports showing the revenues and expenditures of the implemented strategic plan and performance reports? (Caba Perez et al., 2014, p.8)

d: Are disclosed financial data on budget expenditures presented with charts, graphs, or tables? (Gençkaya & Gündoğdu, 2021, p.713)

e: Is there information on projects carried out by the metropolitan municipality? (Carvalho et al., 2020, p.49)

**Dialogue Sub-
Dimensions**

a: Is there information on activities/services/programs carried out for stakeholders?

Stakeholder

Input

b: Is the organization's mission clearly defined?

c: Is the organization's vision clearly defined?

d: Is a calendar of planned events for stakeholders published on the website?

**Disclosure Sub-
Dimensions Criteria**

e: Are periodic reports and current newsletters on activities published? f: Are photographs published along with the activities conducted?

g: Are videos published along with the activities conducted?

h: Are online discussion panels/open forums for suggestions or comments available? (Are there applications allowing stakeholders to discuss specific municipal activities online and published discussion summaries?) (Carvalho et al., 2020, p.48)

a: Is media access open for stakeholder participation? (Are social media platforms used by the metropolitan municipality — such as Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, Wikipedia, etc. — included on the website?)

b: Is there a section where stakeholders can express their main concerns and issues?

**Interactive
Participation**

c: Are downloadable items available on the website? (Audio, videos, Excel, PDF, links, drop-down menus)

d: Can services, transactions, or interactions be conducted entirely online? (Including credit card payments, request/complaint submissions, searchable databases, cookie use, digital signatures)

e: Are there feedback opportunities for stakeholders? (Are there feedback tracking forms for issues such as requests, suggestions, or complaints?) (Midin et al., 2017, p.1676)

Table Note: “Table 3.1. Dimensions of Online Accountability and Evaluation Criteria” was originally created by the author.

4. Findings and Evaluation Based on Criteria

Based on the 22 criteria defined in Table 3.1, the official websites of 30 metropolitan municipalities were examined and their levels of online accountability were evaluated. The resulting data are presented in the table below.

Table 4.2. Online Accountability Levels of Metropolitan Municipalities

Disclosure Dimension					Dialogue Dimension																	
Metropolitan Municipalities	Performance Disclosure				Financial Disclosure					Stakeholder Input								Interactive Participation				
	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	a	b	c	d	e
Adana	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ankara	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Antalya	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Aydın	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Balıkesir	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Denizli	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Diyarbakır	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Erzurum	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Eskişehir	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Gaziantep	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Hatay	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
İstanbul	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
İzmir	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
K.Maraş	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Kayseri	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Kocaeli	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Konya	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Malatya	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Manisa	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mardin	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Mersin	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Muğla	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ordu	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Sakarya	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Samsun	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Şanlıurfa	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Tekirdağ	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Trabzon	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Van	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Table Note: “Table 4.2. Online Accountability Levels of Metropolitan Municipalities” was originally constructed by the author.

Performance Statement has been evaluated in accordance with the specified criteria;

Criterion a – Pursuant to Law No. 5018, in order to implement the principle of transparency, metropolitan municipalities are required to publish their annual activity reports on their official websites. In this context, the fact that 29 metropolitan municipalities include their annual activity reports on their websites indicates a high publication rate, whereas Konya Metropolitan Municipality does not implement such a practice. Kocaeli, Mersin, and Samsun Metropolitan Municipalities serve as examples for other municipalities in terms of ease of access to their official websites and the strengthening of the transparency approach.

Criterion b – Law No. 5018 on Public Financial Management and Control requires municipalities to publish their preliminary budget reports and year-end reports on their websites to ensure budgetary transparency. While 27 metropolitan municipalities include this information on their websites, Erzurum, Konya, and Malatya Metropolitan Municipalities do not provide such data online. In particular, Balıkesir, Kocaeli, Mersin, Samsun, and Trabzon Metropolitan Municipalities present clear and comprehensible financial tables, charts, and graphics on their websites to facilitate stakeholders’ access to budgetary data.

Criterion c – In accordance with Law No. 6085 on the Court of Accounts and Law No. 5018 on Public Financial Management and Control, local administrations are expected to present

their long- and short-term plans to the public transparently, in line with the principle of accountability. While 29 metropolitan municipalities publish long- and short-term activity reports on their websites, Konya Metropolitan Municipality does not provide any information in this regard.

Criterion d – Although Law No. 5393 on Municipalities does not impose a direct obligation for the publication of municipal council meetings, decisions, and minutes online, sharing such information with the public is considered a good governance practice in accordance with the principles of accountability and transparency. Within this scope, 28 metropolitan municipalities publish council agendas, decisions, and minutes on their websites, whereas Manisa Metropolitan Municipality does not share this information. For instance, Ankara Metropolitan Municipality presents council decisions online with video support, while Antalya, Hatay, and Samsun Metropolitan Municipalities provide direct access and open data from previous years to public access.

The Financial Statement has been evaluated in accordance with the specified criteria;

Criterion a – Within the scope of Law No. 5018 on Public Financial Management and Control, public administrations are expected to prepare their budgets and present them to the public. While 29 metropolitan municipalities publish budget information for past and current years on their websites, Konya Metropolitan Municipality does not share such data. For instance, Bursa, İzmir, Mersin, Sakarya, and Samsun Metropolitan Municipalities directly publish budget information on their homepages, supported by tables and documents.

Criterion b – According to the criteria concerning public procurement and purchasing procedures, announcements must be made through specific channels such as the Official Gazette and electronic platforms. Accordingly, 28 metropolitan municipalities announce public tenders via their websites, whereas Erzurum and Konya Metropolitan Municipalities do not provide any information on public tenders on their websites. The live broadcast service of the tender room on the website of Kocaeli Metropolitan Municipality serves as an exemplary practice, and the publication of administrative procedures related to the presentation, evaluation, and finalization of tenders on the website ensures that tender processes are conducted transparently and enhances accountability.

Criterion c – Article 39 of Law No. 5302 stipulates the publication of strategic plans and performance reports. While 29 metropolitan municipalities publish their strategic plans along with performance and financial reports on their websites, Konya Metropolitan Municipality does not include such information. Accordingly, Muğla and Trabzon Metropolitan Municipalities provide easy access to strategic plans and performance reports from their homepages and present these reports in a clear and visual format supported by financial data.

Criterion d – Pursuant to Law No. 5018 on Public Financial Management and Control (PFMC), public administrations are obliged to report financial expenditures transparently. Within this scope, 29 metropolitan municipalities publish budget expenditures in graphical and tabular formats, whereas Konya Metropolitan Municipality does not provide such data. The financial information regarding budget expenditures published by Ankara and Trabzon Metropolitan Municipalities in graphical and tabular formats ensures ease of access and clarity.

Criterion e – The publication of information regarding completed or planned projects on the websites of metropolitan municipalities is of great importance in terms of accountability. While 23 metropolitan municipalities provide detailed information about projects on their websites, such information is not available on the websites of Adana, Antalya, Hatay, Kahramanmaraş, Mardin, Sakarya, and Trabzon Metropolitan Municipalities. In contrast, Malatya, Antalya, and Ankara Metropolitan Municipalities have presented spatial data on their websites by supporting land use related to project planning processes with visuals and videos.

Stakeholder Input has been evaluated in accordance with the specified criteria:

Criterion a – According to Law No. 5216 on Metropolitan Municipalities, metropolitan municipalities are obliged to ensure the transparent delivery of public services. Within this scope, all metropolitan municipalities provide information on their websites regarding the events, activities, and programs conducted for stakeholders, in accordance with the relevant criteria. For example, Samsun, Kocaeli, and Konya Metropolitan Municipalities have directly published their activities and programs on their homepages, facilitated access through explanatory content and visuals, and informed stakeholders via announcements.

Criterion b – While 24 metropolitan municipalities include information on their websites explaining the institution's mission, 6 metropolitan municipalities do not publish such

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information. Publishing the institution's mission, recent activity reports, or future plans and projects on municipal websites is of great importance in terms of accountability.

Criterion c – Information explaining the institution's vision is available on the websites of 25 metropolitan municipalities, whereas 5 metropolitan municipalities do not provide such information. Websites offer insights into how metropolitan municipalities will realize their strategic goals and priority plans, thereby enabling stakeholders to gain a transparent perspective on the municipality's future orientations.

Criterion d – While 26 metropolitan municipalities publish planned event calendars on their websites, Hatay, Mardin, Samsun, and Van Metropolitan Municipalities do not share this information. For instance, Malatya Metropolitan Municipality presents its event calendar on the homepage, supported by visuals.

Criterion e – News bulletins and announcements published on the websites of 30 metropolitan municipalities generally serve a one-way informational purpose, offering content focused on information dissemination. This situation has a decisive impact on the capacity of bulletins to provide meaningful and accurate information to stakeholders and on strengthening accountability regarding the actions and decisions of municipal administrations.

Criterion f – 28 metropolitan municipalities publish photographs related to organized events and activities on their websites, whereas Hatay and Van Metropolitan Municipalities do not share such content. By sharing photographs of events via their websites, metropolitan municipalities provide more information in a format that stakeholders can easily access.

Criterion g – While 25 metropolitan municipalities publish videos related to their events and activities on their websites, 5 metropolitan municipalities do not include such videos. Establishing audio-visual communication with stakeholders through municipal websites and effectively utilizing multimedia elements is important for accountability.

Criterion h – Online discussion panels of varying levels are available on the websites of Adana, Aydın, İstanbul, Kayseri, and Kocaeli Metropolitan Municipalities, whereas the remaining 25 metropolitan municipalities do not have such panels on their websites. Online discussion panels are important platforms that offer open communication channels for addressing stakeholder

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concerns and enabling responses through data. These platforms facilitate direct interaction with stakeholders, thereby enhancing participation and traceability.

Interactive Participation has been evaluated in accordance with the specified criteria:

Criterion a – All metropolitan municipalities have social media platforms (Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram) accessible via their official websites. These media applications enable municipalities to establish communication with stakeholders within an organizational context. Platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube facilitate the sharing of videos, visuals, and texts, thereby supporting collaborative processes among stakeholders.

Criterion b – Pursuant to Law No. 5393, all metropolitan municipalities provide stakeholders with the opportunity to submit requests and complaints through dedicated platforms available on each municipality’s website. In addition to practices that promote interaction between Central Government and Local Administrations, the Presidential Communication Center (CİMER) application also supports effective stakeholder participation in various services offered by metropolitan municipalities at the local level.

Criterion c – On the websites of 30 metropolitan municipalities, shared data is presented to stakeholders in various formats, particularly in downloadable formats such as PDF, ensuring re-accessibility when needed. These downloadable contents function as effective tools for municipalities to fulfill their responsibilities toward the public, facilitating the monitoring and evaluation of public services.

Criterion d – With the Additional Article 3 of Law No. 5393, municipalities have begun to conduct administrative procedures related to their assigned duties and services via their websites. With the establishment of official websites of metropolitan municipalities, paper-based procedures have started to be transferred to digital platforms. Many public services such as health, tax, electricity, water, and natural gas payments can now be carried out electronically through the “online transactions” section of municipal websites.

Criterion e – Law No. 4982 on the Right to Information defines the obligation of public institutions to provide information to stakeholders. Within this scope, 30 metropolitan municipalities allow stakeholders to submit information requests and provide feedback on municipal activities via their websites. Metropolitan municipalities can collect requests and

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This evaluation conducted through the websites of metropolitan municipalities in Türkiye reveals that the legal regulations and reforms supporting the implementation of online accountability have established a robust legal infrastructure that enables municipalities to fulfill their administrative procedures and public service responsibilities. While metropolitan municipalities demonstrate a high level of compliance in terms of information accessibility, it is observed that online discussion panels and feedback mechanisms promoting participatory governance are implemented in a more limited manner. This indicates that despite strong legal compliance, full realization of online accountability has not yet been achieved, and certain deficiencies persist in enabling stronger stakeholder interaction through digital platforms.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

In Türkiye, there is currently no comprehensive study focusing specifically on the dimensions of “disclosure and dialogue” within the framework of online accountability practices implemented through the websites of metropolitan municipalities. In this study, the criteria defined in relation to disclosure and dialogue sub-dimensions, along with financial information, performance reports, and stakeholder participation, have been evaluated through data analysis based on the websites of metropolitan municipalities. Moreover, although there is no legal regulation that directly refers to online accountability practices, these practices have been addressed within the framework of various reforms and regulations that lay the foundations and prepare the ground for their development. In this context, the e-Government Gateway has constituted a significant turning point in the digital delivery of public services, thereby facilitating stakeholders’ access to public services. The financial information and performance reports provided by municipalities via their websites emerge as critical elements that directly affect the principles of transparency, participation, and accountability. Through data analysis, municipalities can more accurately identify stakeholder needs and enhance participation, while relevant legal regulations that enable access to publicly available financial data can make significant contributions to strengthening trust between municipalities and stakeholders.

Metropolitan municipalities in Türkiye, in line with the legal regulations enacted within the reform process aimed at implementing online accountability, provide stakeholders with direct

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access by publishing annual activity reports, budgets, plans, council decisions, projects, visuals related to activities, request-complaint sections, and feedback forms on their official websites. This digital transformation has not only improved service quality but also enabled the state to be “one click away” from stakeholders and to provide services 24/7. The traceability of every stage of services offered through the websites of metropolitan municipalities ensures that these services are accessible and widely utilized. The effective use of metropolitan municipalities’ websites constitutes a significant component of online accountability.

As a result of the evaluations, it is emphasized that all metropolitan municipalities’ websites should have a more consistent design and that their content should be structured in accordance with e-Government standards. Ensuring that online services are easily accessible from the homepage will enable stakeholders to quickly reach the information they need and promote interaction. Furthermore, online discussion panels are recommended as an important tool for stakeholders to share their opinions and for municipalities to enhance accountability. Feedback forms allow municipalities to quickly identify and resolve service deficiencies. Email notification systems and free subscription options offered via websites also present effective methods to increase participation and ensure stakeholder involvement in processes. In conclusion, web-based accountability transcends the traditional understanding of accountability by enabling stakeholders to interact more effectively with municipalities and to hold them accountable. This process, driven by technological advancement, not only enhances the transparency and accountability of municipalities but also promotes stakeholder participation at a broader level.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, Z. A., & Rusdianto, R. (2020). Impact of transparency and accountability on trust and intention to donate cash Waqf in Islamic microfinance institution *Shirkah: Journal of Economics and Business*, 5(2), 197-227.
- Ammons, D. N. & Rivenbark, W. C. (2008). Factors influencing the use of performance data to improve municipal services: Evidence from the North Carolina benchmarking project. *Public Administration Review*, 68(2), 304-318.
- Ariesmansyah, A., Lestari, H. A., Yodiansyah. H., Chakim Riza H. M. & Junaedi. R. W. (2021). Creativity to innovation: What lesson learned from digital transformation in financial accountability in government practice *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*, 4(4), November, 14061-14072.
- Aytar, O. (2022). Evaluation of the corporate governance system and principles from the perspective of internal audit in the public sector. *Denetışim Journal*, 0(24), 5–21.
- Bakar, N. B. A. & Saleh, Z. (2016). Extent of disclosure in the annual reports of Malaysian federal statutory bodie *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 158.
- Biricikođlu, H. & Eryılmaz, B. (2011). Kamu yönetiminde hesap verebilirlik ve etik. *İş Ahlaki Dergisi*, 4(7), 19-45, Mayıs.
- Brusca, I. & Montesinos, V. (2016). Implementing performance reporting in local government: A cross-countries comparison. *Public Performance & Management Review*, 39(3), 506-534, DOI: 10.1080/15309576.2015.1137768.
- Caba Perez, C. M., Rodiguez Bolivar, M. P. & Lopez Hernandez, M. A. (2014). The determinants of government financial reports online. *Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences*, 0(42), 5-31.
- Carvalho, A., Ferrira. R. M. & Lima. (2020). Web disclosure of institutional information in nonprofit organizations: An approach in portuguese charitie *International Review on Public and Nonprofit Marketing*, 1(17), 41-58.
- Cooley, A. (2020). Comparative analysis of online accountability practices in three sectors: Private, public and nonprofit accounting. *Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 33(6), 1423-1445.

- Çınar, F. (2015). The role of stakeholder participation in the relationship between the principle of accountability and institutional performance: An implementation in hospital enterprises. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Vizyoner Dergisi*, 6(13), 12–30.
- Dubnick, M. (2005). Accountability and the promise of performance: In search of the mechanism *Public Performance & Management Review*, 28(3), 376-417.
- Dumont, E. G. (2013). Transparency or accountability? The purpose of online technologies for nonprofit *International Review of Public Administration*, 18(3), 7-29.
- Eroğlu, T. H. (2019). The never-ending symphony: Performance auditing in municipalities. *Uluslararası Yönetim Akademisi Dergisi*, 2(3), 546–556.
- García, A. C. & García-García, J. (2010). Determinants of online reporting of accounting information by Spanish local government authorities *Local Government Studies*, 36(5), 679-695.
- García Tabuyo, M., Sáez-Martín, A. & Caba-Pérez, M. D. (2015). Mandatory versus voluntary disclosures: Drivers of proactive information provision by local governments in Central America", *Information Development*, 32(4), 1199–1215.
- Gajewski, J. & Li Li, F. (2015). Can Internet-based disclosure reduce information asymmetry? *Advances in accounting, incorporating advances in international accounting*, 31, 115–124.
- Gençkaya, Ö. F., Gündoğdu, H. G. & Aytekin, A. (2021). Evaluation of metropolitan municipalities' websites in terms of governance principles. *Eskişehir Osmangazi Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 16(3), 705–726.
- İlgin, H. Ö. & Ulupınar, Ş. C. (2020). The effectiveness of websites as a promotional tool: Social services and social responsibility practices of metropolitan municipalities. *Journal of Emerging Economies and Policy*, 5(2), 108–120.
- Kara, H., & Karakılçık, Y. (2016). Audit of local governments within the scope of Law No. 5018: Innovations introduced, practices, and encountered deficiencies. *Ordu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Sosyal Bilimler Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 6(3), 727–738.

- Khoufi, N. & Khoufi, W. (2018). An empirical examination of the determinants of audit report delay in France. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 700-714.
- Kim, & Lee, J. (2017). Citizen participation, process, and transparency in local government: An exploratory study. *The Policy Studies Journal*, 47(4), 1020-1041.
- Kloot, L. (1999). Performance measurement and accountability in Victorian local government. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 12(7), December, Australia,
- Kluvers, R. (2003). Accountability for performance in local government. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 1, April.
- Lappas, G., Triantafillidou, A. & Kani, A. (2022). Harnessing the power of dialogue: examining the impact of facebook content on citizens engagement. *Local Government Studies*, 48(1), 87-106.
- Lee, R. L., & Joseph, R. C. (2012). Survival of the fittest: Online accountability in complex organizational population *Proceedings*, 30, 171-175, March.
- Lee, L. & Joseph, C. (2013), An examination of web disclosure and organizational transparency. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(6), 2218-2224, November.
- Lourenço, P. R., Sá E, M. P., Jorge, & Pattaro, F. A. (2013). Online transparency for accountability: One assessing model and two application *Electronic Journal of e-Government*, 11(2), 280-292.
- Lourenço R. P. & Serra. L. (2014) “An Online Transparency for Accountability Maturity Model”, INESC Coimbra, Portugal Faculty of Economics, University of Coimbra, Portuga, LNCS 8653, pp. 35-46.
- Midin, M., Joseph, C. & Mohamed, N. (2017). Promoting societal governance: Stakeholders' engagement disclosure on Malaysian local authorities' website *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142, 1672-1683.
- Mulgan, R. (2000). *Accountability: An ever-expanding concept*. *Public Administration*, Australian National University, 78(3), 555-573.

- Nair, R., Arshad, R., Muda, R. & Joharry, A. (2022). Web-disclosure practices for transparency and the sustainability of non-profit organisation *International Review on Public and Nonprofit Marketing*, 1-23, July.
- Özata, M. & Sevinç, İ. (2010). Information systems and e-transformation in Turkish public administration. Eğitim Akademi Yayınları, 1st Edition, February, Konya.
- Patrucco, A. S., Agasisti, T., & Glas, A. H. (2021). Structuring public procurement in local governments: the effect of centralization, standardization and digitalization on performance. *Public performance & management review*, 44(3), 630-656.
- Putri, P. P., Damayanti, R. & Hapsari, A. N. (2021). Village fund allocation practice: The investigation of accountability and transparency. *JIA (Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi)*, 6(2), 455-470, December.
- Roberts, C. N. (2002). Keeping public officials accountable through Dialogue: Resolving the accountability paradox. *Public Administration Review*, 62(6), 658-669, November.
- Robbins, M. D., Simonsen, B. & Feldman, B. (2008). Citizens and resource allocation: Improving decision making with interactive web-based citizen participation. *Public Administration Review*, 68(3), 564-575.
- Sary Kezia. A., Karim, A., Irawan, B., & Hananah, N. (2021). Performance accountability system in online-based government institution. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Manajemen*, 15(1), 65-80.
- Shahip, M. H. & Risky, R. F. (2017). Accountability in the internet era: A Lesson from local governments in Indonesia. *Hasanuddin Economics and Business Review*, 1(1), 57-74, June.
- Saxton, G. D. & Gou, C. (2011). Accountability online: Understanding the web-based accountability practices of nonprofit organization *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 40(2), 270-295.
- Saxton, G. D., Neely, G. D. & Gou, C. (2014). Web disclosure and the market for charitable contribution *Journal of Accounting and Public*, (33)2, 127-144.

- Sezer, Ö., & Büyükpınar, R. (2021). The new public management approach and localization policies in Turkey. *Uluslararası Batı Karadeniz Sosyal ve Beşeri Bilimler Dergisi*, 5(1), 80–105.
- Sintejeanu, M. A., & Farcas, T. V. (2017). E-Governance in Public Sector: Online Transparency for Romanian Hospitals. *Journal of Accounting & Management (2284-9459)*, 7(1).
- Sun, Y. & Sundar, (2022). *Exploring the effects of interactive dialogue in improving user control for explainable online symptom controller* Extended Summaries of Human Factors in Computer Systems at the CHI Conference, 1-7, April.
- Şat, N. (2016). An analysis of metropolitan municipalities' websites in Turkey. *Turkish Journal of Administration*, 482, 183–238.
- Trabelsia, Labelleb, R. & Dumontier P. (2008). Incremental voluntary disclosure on corporate websites, determinants and consequence *Journal of Contemporary Accounting & Economics*, 4(2), 120-155, December.
- Tejedo-Romero, F., Araujo, J. F. F. E., Tejada, Á., & Ramírez, Y. (2022). E-government mechanisms to enhance the participation of citizens and society: Exploratory analysis.
- Yaman, A. & Gökalp, G. (2017). The impact of new public management reforms on local governments. *Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 1(4), 1–12.